

PREDICTED SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF APERTURES IN LARGE ENCLOSURES AS MEASURED BY MIL-STD-285 AND OTHER METHODS

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Abstract

Polarizability theory has been applied to the problem of predicting the shielding effectiveness of a conductive shield with a well defined aperture. Shielding effectiveness was defined by both MIL-STD-285 (ratio of the fields at a prescribed point with and without the shield in place) and the ratio of the magnetic field outside and inside of a shield. Relatively simple relationships were derived if the aperture was electrically small and the shield behaved like a plane conducting sheet. These relationships were consistent with measured values, and allow calibration apertures to be used to establish the credibility of shielding effectiveness measurements.

Introduction

One of the advantages of surface transfer impedance has been the availability of calibration standards, such as solid pipes and pipes with holes, whose electromagnetic performance can be calculated from the geometry of the sample and the properties of the material from which it was made. Such calibration samples are useful, not only for validating the measurement, but also for providing perspective into what sort of values are reasonable in practical circumstances. Generally, such calibration samples have not been available for enclosure shielding measurements. Fortunately, the shielding effectiveness of a conductive shield with a well defined aperture can be predicted using polarizability theory and the definition of shielding effectiveness. This paper will present the theoretical development associated with such a prediction.

Assume that the aperture is in a plane conductive sheet or on the wall of an enclosure that is so large that the reflections from the other walls are insignificant compared to the fields that penetrate the aperture. Further assume that the frequency is high enough so that the conductive wall is several skin depths thick, (therefore current diffusion is insignificant) but low enough so that the transmitter loop and aperture can be approximated by a magnetic dipole. Consider magnetic shielding effectiveness only.

Figure 1 shows two ways of orienting the loops used to generate and measure the magnetic fields used for determining the shielding effectiveness of shields. The coplanar arrangement is implied for MIL-STD-285 and the parallel arrangement is used by some other standards.

The coplanar orientation is consistent with the boundary conditions imposed by electromagnetic theory (magnetic flux density is parallel to surface of conducting surface). This paper will only consider the coplanar orientation.

Figure 1. Coplanar Vs. Parallel Orientation

MIL-STD-285 Shielding Effectiveness

Figure 2 shows the geometrical arrangement of the transmitting and receiving loop antennae. The MIL-STD-285 definition of shielding effectiveness is the ratio of the field at a point with and without the shield in place. The shielding effectiveness according to this definition will be designated SE285. Thus:

$$SE_{285} = \frac{H_{ref}}{H_{\theta}} \quad (1)$$

The top portion of Figure 2 shows the arrangement for measuring the magnetic field (H_{ref}) without the shield. The bottom portion shows the arrangement for measuring the magnetic field with the shield in place. Also shown in Figure 2 are the incident field, H_{inc} , and the magnetic field on the surface of the shield, H_{θ} , sometimes called the short circuit magnetic field.

Figure 2. Geometry Used in Predicting Shielding of an Aperture

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The near field from a magnetic dipole falls off as $1/r^3$. Thus

$$H_{\text{ref}} = \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^3 H_{\text{inc}} \quad (2)$$

Due to reflection, the surface field at the shield, H_0 , is twice the incident field at that point.

$$H_0 = 2 H_{\text{inc}} \quad (3)$$

An aperture with a magnetic polarization α_m is replaced with an equivalent dipole loop. This allows the magnetic field due to the aperture (H_θ) to be calculated at a distance r_3 in front of the aperture.

$$H_\theta = \left(\frac{\alpha_m}{2r}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r_3}\right)^3 H_0 \sin\phi \cos\theta \quad (4)$$

where θ is the angle between the measured magnetic field and the magnetic moment, and ϕ is the angle subtended by a vector from the center of the aperture to the observation point and the surface of the wall. Combining the Equations 1, 2, 3, and 4, one obtains:

$$SE_{285} = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha_m}\right) \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^3 \frac{(r_3)^3}{2 \sin\phi \cos\theta} \quad (5)$$

The maximum field occurs directly in front of the aperture ($\phi = 90$, $\theta = 0$) and both of the trigonometric terms are equal to 1. Equation 5 then becomes:

$$SE_{285} = \left(\frac{\pi}{\alpha_m}\right) \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^3 (r_3)^3 \quad (6)$$

For a circular aperture of radius a , the magnetic polarizability is [1]:

$$\alpha_m = 4 \frac{a^3}{3} \quad (7)$$

Substituting this into Equation 6:

$$SE_{285} = \left(\frac{3\pi}{4}\right) \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^3 \left(\frac{r_3}{a}\right)^3 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{If } r_1 = r_3 = \frac{r_2}{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} SE_{285} &= \left(\frac{3\pi}{32}\right) \left(\frac{r_3}{a}\right)^3 \\ &= 0.295 \left(\frac{r_3}{a}\right)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

If $r_3 = 16$ inches = .406 m

$$SE_{285} = 19.74 \times 10^{-3} a^{-3} \quad (10)$$

Converting to decibels, Equation 10 becomes:

$$SE_{285} \text{ (dB)} = -34 - 60 \log(a) \quad (11)$$

For an aperture with a radius of 0.0254 m (1 inch), the predicted shielding effectiveness is:

$$SE_{285} = 61.7 \text{ dB} \quad (12)$$

Figure 3 shows the shielding effectiveness of a set of calibration apertures as measured by several RF leak detectors [2]. The shielding effectiveness of the 2 inch diameter (1 inch radius) aperture is about 60 dB. The agreement between experiment and theory is remarkably good.

Figure 3. RF Leak Detector Measurement of Calibrated Apertures

Note that the shielding effectiveness is a strong function (cubed dependence) of the distance between the shield and the measurement location. Thus shielding effectiveness is not an intrinsic electromagnetic parameter.

Surface Magnetic Field Attenuation

Sometimes an alternative definition of shielding effectiveness is useful, namely, the ratio of the surface field on the exterior to the magnetic field at a prescribed distance inside of the conductive shield. This is called surface magnetic field attenuation and is designated MFA. Using the magnetic fields defined in Figure 2:

$$MFA = \frac{H_0}{H_\theta} \quad (13)$$

The same relationships previously obtained (Equations 4 and 7) can be used to predict the shielding effectiveness of an aperture under these conditions. The resulting shielding effectiveness is:

$$SE = 13.5 + 60 \log r_3 - 60 \log a \quad (14)$$

For an aperture with a radius $a = 0.0254$ m and for $r_3 = 0.15$ m (6 inches), the predicted magnetic field attenuation is 59.7 dB. Note that this is the ratio of the magnetic field at two points (inside and outside of the shield) and not the ratio of fields with and without the shields in place.

Figure 4 shows the measured surface magnetic field attenuation of a set of calibration apertures [3]. The measured surface magnetic field attenuation

for a 2 inch diameter aperture is about 60 dB, which is in good agreement with the 59.7 dB predicted by theory.

Figure 4. Laboratory Measurement of Magnetic Field Attenuation of Calibrated Apertures Using the SPEHS Technique

The surface magnetic attenuation has the same distance cubed dependence as the shielding effectiveness. Consequently, neither are intrinsic electromagnetic parameters.

Conclusions

Polarizability theory has been applied to the problem of predicting the magnetic field shielding effectiveness of a conductive shield with a well defined aperture. The resulting relationships can be used to predict the shielding effectiveness as defined by MIL-STD-285 and surface magnetic field attenuation. Theory and experiment are in agreement. Shielding effectiveness and surface magnetic field attenuation are both strong functions of the distance between the measurement location and the shield. Thus, both are not intrinsic electromagnetic parameters.

References

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